

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation Of Herbal Anti-Aging Cream Using Clerodendrum Infortunatum And Eclipta Prostrata

Devika K V ^{1*}, Sana Majeed¹, Manjima K¹, Safvana C¹, Sneha P K¹, Vyshnavy Devy D K²

¹Bachelor of Pharmacy, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Pharmaceutical Science and Research, Trikaripur, Kasaragod, India, 671310.

²Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacognosy, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Pharmaceutical Science and Research, Trikaripur, Kasaragod, India, 671310.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 17 Oct 2024

Keywords:

Eclipta prostrata (L.),
Clerodendrum infortunatum,
Anti-oxidant, DPPH(2,2-
diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl),
Anti-aging.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13944546

ABSTRACT

Herbal formulation is a dosage form consisting of one or more one fresh herbs of processed herbs in particular quantities to provide specific nutritional, cosmetic benefits and are meant for diagnose, treatment and mitigation of disease in human beings. Herbal anti-aging creams are semi-solid dosage forms in which natural ingredients are dispersed to reduce the production of free radicals in skin and manage skin properties for a very long time. It is used for achieving longevity of good health by reducing skin disorders like hyper pigmentation, skin aging, skin wrinkling and rough skin texture. The aim of the present work is to reveal the Pharmacognostic, phytochemical, anti-oxidant activity for the formulation and evaluation of herbal anti-aging cream. The required materials were collected from Kasaragod and subjected to maceration. Later, Pharmacognostic studies like microscopical evaluation, ash value and extractive value were carried out. The preliminary phytochemical studies were carried out using solvents like water and ethanol. Aqueous and ethanolic extract was used for the study of anti-oxidant activity.

INTRODUCTION

Anti-aging cosmetics is the branch of cosmetics which deal with the removal of aging and wrinkle of the skin. They are predominantly moisturizer-based cosmeceutical skin care products which are marked with the promise

of making the customer look younger by reducing, masking or preventing the signs of aging[1]. Herbal antiaging creams are semisolid dosage forms in which natural ingredients are dispersed to reduce the production of free

***Corresponding Author:** Devika K V

Address: Bachelor of Pharmacy, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Pharmaceutical Science and Research, Trikaripur, Kasaragod, India, 671310.

Email ✉: devikakarunakaran2000@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

radicals in skin and manage skin properties for a very long time. Herbs and plants are used for achieving longevity of good health by reducing skin disorders like hyper pigmentation, skin aging, skin wrinkling and rough skin texture. The synthetic or natural ingredients present helps in supporting health, texture and integrity of skin by maintaining its elasticity, anti-oxidant potential and photoprotection. The present work is to develop herbal anti-aging cream to be applied for treatment of skin aging and removal of wrinkle effect of skin. Herbal anti-aging cream is prepared by using potent medicinal plants such as Clerodendrum infortunatum and Eclipta prostrata(L.). All of these plants have an effective antioxidant activity. By incorporating the leaf extract of Clerodendrum infortunatum and Eclipta prostrata, herbal anti-aging cream with antioxidant activity can be prepared. For evaluating the antioxidant activity, we use DPPH assay method.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Collection of plant material

The fresh leaves of Clerodendrum infortunatum, Eclipta prostrata(L.) were collected from Kasaragod district, Kerala(India)in the month of March 2024.

Authentication of plant material

The plant material was collected from Kasaragod district, Kerala (India) in the month of March 2024.The plant material was identified and authenticated by Smitha K O, Assistant Professor, Horticulture Department, College of Agriculture, Padnakkad, Kasaragod, Kerala.

Extraction of plant material

Extraction of Clerodendrum infortunatum, Eclipta prostrata was carried out separately by maceration.

The freshly cleaned leaves of Clerodendrum infortunatum were air dried for 72 hours at room

temperature and then ground into fine powder. 250 g of powder was extracted by maceration for 24 hours with 500 ml ethanol in a stoppered flask with occasional shaking at 25oC and filtered through whatmann filter paper No 1. Then the crude extract was evaporated to dryness. The extract was preserved after drying and stored at 4oC in air tight container until needed[2]. The freshly collected leaves of Eclipta prostrata were kept under running tap water and dried at room temperature. Then the material was ground into coarse powdered 50 gm of leaf powder was extracted by maceration in 250 ml water. After 72 hours leaf extract were filtered through whatmann filter paper No 1 and the solvent was evaporated. The extract were stored in air tight container until needed[3].

Preliminary phytochemical screening

The extract of selected plants were subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening to detect various phytoconstituents like alkaloids, glycosides, flavonoids, saponins, tannins and phenolic compounds, carbohydrates, proteins and amino acids and fats and oil[4].

Formulation of herbal anti-aging cream[5]

Herbal anti-aging cream were prepared by using the extract of Clerodendrum infortunatum and Eclipta prostrata, by incorporating it with other ingredients like stearic acid, cetyl alcohol, glycerin, methyl paraben, triethanol amine and water. Three different formulations were prepared by changing the concentration of ingredients of cream bases as shown in table 1.

Procedure:

- a. Stearic acid and other oil soluble ingredients like cetyl alcohol, glycerin and triethanol amine
- b. were dissolved in the oil phase and heated to 75oC.
- c. Methyl paraben were dissolved in the aqueous phase and heated to 75oC.

- d. After heating the aqueous phase was added in portions to the oil phase with continuous stirring.
- e. When the cream base begins to cool, add the extracts to it and stir well until a smooth cream is obtained.

EVALUATION OF HERBAL ANTI-AGING CREAM[6]

Physical evaluation

The cream were evaluated manually for its colour, odour, texture and state.

Irritancy

1cm² area were marked at the left hand dorsal surface. Then the cream was applied to that area and the time was noted. Then it is checked for irritancy, erythema and edema if any for an interval of upto 24 hrs and reported.

Washability

A small amount of cream was applied on the hand and it is then washed with tap water.

PH

0.5gm was taken and dispersed in 50ml distilled water and then PH was measured by using digital PH meter.

Greasiness

Here the cream was applied on the skin surface in the form of smear and checked if the smear was oily or grease-like.

Spreadability

The spreadability was expressed in terms of time in seconds taken by two glass slides to slip from the cream, placed in between the slides, under certain load. Lesser the time taken for separation of the two slides, better the spreadability.

$$S = m \times l/t$$

Where, S=Spreadability

m=Weight tied to the upper slide

l=Length of the glass slide

t=Time taken in sec

INVITRO ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY

DPPH Assay method[7]

The free RSA of the dilute leaf extracts was tested using a 1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl hydrazyl (DPPH) technique.

Procedure:

1. A total of 24 milligrams of DPPH were dissolved in 100 mL of methanol for making the stock solution.
2. In a test tube, 3 mL DPPH workable solutions were combined with 100 μ L of leaf extract.
3. Three milliliters of solution containing DPPH in 100 μ L of methanol is often given as a standard.
4. After that, the tubes were kept in complete darkness for 30 min.
5. The absorbance was therefore determined at 517 nm.
6. The following formula was used to compute the percentage of antioxidant activity.

$$\% \text{ of antioxidant activity} = \frac{[Ac-As]}{Ac} \times 100$$

Where; Ac-Control reaction absorbance.

As-Testing specimen absorbance.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Extraction of plant material

The extraction of dried leaves of Clerodendrum infortunatum and Eclipta prostrata were carried out by maceration process by using suitable solvent as shown in fig 1. The extracts obtained were collected and concentrated which is then weighed and kept in a desiccator until used for further studies.

Preliminary phytochemical screening

The plant leaves were macerated with different solvents and the extract thus obtained is subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening to detect various phytochemical constituents mentioned in table 2.

Formulation of herbal anti-aging cream

Herbal anti-aging cream were prepared as shown in fig 2.

Physical evaluation

The physical parameters such as state, colour, odour, texture was checked and the result is as given in table 3.

Irritancy

The formulation shows no irritancy.

Washability

The formation shows good washability.

PH

The PH of the prepared formulation was determined by using digital PH meter. The PH of the formulations are shown in table 4.

Greasiness

The formulations are non-greasy.

Spreadability

The spreadability of the formulation was evaluated and the result is shown in table 5.

INVITRO ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY

The antioxidant activity of the plant extract was done by DPPH free radical scavenging assay method. The antioxidant activity was calculated in terms of %inhibition which is shown in table

6 and using graph 1. The main aim of the study is to make herbal anti-aging cream by using medicinal plants such as Clerodendrum infortunatum and Eclipta prostrata(L.). All of these plants have an effective anti-

oxidant activity.

The plant material was subjected to maceration process by using solvents like ethanol and water and then the extract was taken for preliminary phytochemical screening. From the result, ethanol gave more active constituents in case of Clerodendrum infortunatum and water gave more active constituents in case of Eclipta prostrata. The presence of major constituents such as flavonoid, phenolic compounds contribute to antioxidant activity which is beneficial for the anti-aging activity. The three different formulations of anti-aging cream containing leaf extract were prepared and the results revealed that the formulation F2 has better acceptability in terms of evaluation tests like PH and spreadability. The

anti-aging activity was measured invitro by DPPH free radical scavenging assay and then the percentage inhibition was calculated. From this results, the cream was considered to be effective for the treatment of aging of skin.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to acknowledge my guide Mrs. Vyshnavy Devy D K, Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacognosy, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Pharmaceutical Science and Research for her constant guidance and valuable suggestions and encouragement. We are deeply indebted to Prof. Dr. M. Paridhavi, M Pharm, PhD, FABAP, Principal, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Pharmaceutical Science and Research, for his valuable advice and support to make the study successful. We also extend our sincere thanks to all teachers, who helped us for the completion of this dissertation.

REFERENCES

1. Shanbhag S, Nayak A, Narayan R, Nayak UY. Anti-aging and Sunscreens: Paradigm Shift in Cosmetics. Adv Pharm Bull. 2019 Aug;9(3):348-359.
2. Rej S, Dutta M, Jamal S, Das S, Chatterjee S. Study of phytochemical constituents and antibacterial activity of Clerodendrum infortunatum. Asian Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical Science. 2014;4(4):187-95 .
3. Pukumpuang W, Chansakaow S, Tragoolpua Y. Antioxidant activity, phenolic compound content and phytochemical constituents of Eclipta prostrata (Linn.) Linn. Chiang Mai J Sci. 2014 Jul 1;41(3):568-76.
4. Shaikh JR, Patil M. Qualitative tests for preliminary phytochemical screening: An overview. International Journal of Chemical Studies. 2020 Mar 1;8(2):603-8.
5. Savita M, Jeevan P, Nikita K, Manoj G. Formulation and Evaluation of anti-acne and

anti-aging cream using pomegranate flower and banana peel.2023.

6. Matangi SP, Mamidi SA, Raghavamma ST, Nadendla RR. Formulation and evaluation of anti aging poly herbal cream. *skin*. 2014;5(6).
7. Baliyan S, Mukherjee R, Priyadarshini A, Vibhuti A, Gupta A, Pandey RP, Chang CM. Determination of Antioxidants by DPPH Radical Scavenging Activity and Quantitative

Phytochemical Analysis of *Ficus religiosa*. *Molecules*. 2022 Feb 16;27(4):1326.

HOW TO CITE: Devika K V , Sana Majeed , Manjima K , Safvana C , Sneha P K , Vyshnavy Devy D K, Formulation And Evaluation Of Herbal Anti-Aging Cream Using *Clerodendrum Infortunatum* And *Eclipta Prostrata*, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 10, 923-931. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13944546>

Table 1 : Formulation Of Herbal Anti-Aging Cream

INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3
Clerodendrum infortnatum extract	2.5	2.5	2.5
Eclipta prostrata extract	1.5	1.5	1.5
Stearic acid	13	11	10
Cetyl alcohol	2	4	3
Glycerin	3	3	3
Methyl paraben	0.02	0.02	0.02
Triethanol amine	Q S	Q S	Q S

Preparing the cream using same quantity of each extracts and by varying the quantity of the cream base.

Table 2 : Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

Sl. No.	Chemical constituents	Clerodendrum infortunatum (Ethanol extract)	Eclipta prostrata(Water extract)
1	Carbohydrate	+	+
2	Proteins	-	+
3	Glycosides	-	+
4	Alkaloids	-	+
5	Tannins	+	+
6	Saponins	+	+
7	Flavonoids	+	+
8	Fats and oils	-	-

Each plant extracts are taken for phytochemical screening. The sign “-” means absence and “+” means presence of the particular phytochemicals.

Table 3 : Physical Parameter

SI. No.	Specification	F1	F2	F3
1	State	Semi solid	Semi solid	Semi solid
2	colour	Pale green	Pale green	Pale green
3	odour	characteristic	characteristic	characteristic
4	texture	smooth	smooth	smooth

State, colour, odour and texture of three formulations.

Table 4 : Ph Of The Formulation

Sl. No.	Formulations	pH
1	F1	6.1
2	F2	5.48
3	F3	5.9

PH of the formulation using PH meter.

Table 5 : Spreadability Of The Formulation

Sl. No.	Formulation	Spreadability (g.cm/sec)
1	F1	30
2	F2	28
3	F3	25

The spreadability of three formulations were obtained by using the equation. determined by using glass slides and the values are

Table 6 : Invitro Antioxidant Activity

Groups	Concentration ($\mu\text{m/ml}$)	Absorbance at 517nm	%Inhibition
Control	-	0.1366	-
Eclipta prostrata extract	100	0.086	37.04
	200	0.075	45.09
	300	0.054	60.46
	400	0.041	69.98
	500	0.035	74.37
Clerodendrum infortunatum extract	100	0.097	28.98
	200	0.086	39.23
	300	0.070	48.75
	400	0.064	53.14
	500	0.050	63.39
Ascorbic acid	100	0.071	48.02
	200	0.054	60.46
	300	0.034	75.10
	400	0.026	80.96
	500	0.014	89.75

The antioxidant activity of each plant extract were determined by DPPH assay method, using Ascorbic acid as standard and methanol as blank at 517nm in UV spectrophotometer.

Graph 1 : Antioxidant activity

Antioxidant activity of both the extracts and ascorbic acid (standard) were compared.

Fig 1 : Extracts of leaves

Leaves of each plant were extracted by maceration using different solvents.

Fig 2 : Formulation of herbal anti-aging cream

Tables and figure titles and legend :

TABLE 1 : FORMULATION OF HERBAL ANTI-AGING CREAM

Here the ingredients used for preparing the herbal anti-aging cream were taken in an appropriate quantity.

TABLE 2 : PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING

Each plant extracts are taken for phytochemical screening. The sign “-” means absence and “+” means presence of the particular phytochemicals.

TABLE 3 : PHYSICAL PARAMETER

State, colour, odour and texture of three formulations.

TABLE 4 : P^H OF THE FORMULATION

P^H of the formulation using P^H meter.

TABLE 5 : SPREADABILITY OF THE FORMULATION

The spreadability of three formulations were determined by using glass slides and the values are obtained by using the equation.

TABLE 6 : INVITRO ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY

The antioxidant activity of each plant extract were determined by DPPH assay method, using Ascorbic acid as standard and methanol as blank at 517nm in UV spectrophotometer.

Graph 1 : Antioxidant activity

Antioxidant activity of both the extracts and ascorbic acid (standard) were compared.

Fig 1 : Extracts of leaves

Leaves of each plant were extracted by maceration using different solvents.

Fig 2 : Formulation of herbal anti-aging cream